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Social Development Pathways: Church Mission at Poso Kota Bersaudara¹ in Recovery of Poso Quarter Century Post conflict

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Abstract

This research evaluates the role of the Christian Church in social development in Poso Kota Bersaudara, 25 years after the conflict. The study aims to understand the church's successes and challenges in rebuilding conflict-affected communities. The conflict in Poso (1998-2001) caused significant damage and required extensive reconstruction. The research uses qualitative methods, including literature review, field observation, and interviews. Findings reveal the significant role of the church in social development, including psychological support, education, health, and reconciliation. Church programs have had a positive impact on communities. Challenges, however, include the need for increased interchurch cooperation, overcoming local and denominational boundaries of influence, and promoting a unified vision of religious moderation. The study recommends the development of inclusive strategies for broader, sustainable impact on social development. It provides insights into the role of churches in reconciliation and social development in post-conflict areas, emphasizing the need for continued support to sustain and develop programs. In this way, the church can continue to contribute to peace and prosperity in Poso Kota Bersaudara by supporting holistic recovery that includes spiritual, psychological and socio-economic aspects.

Keywords:

Social Development Mission, Poso, Post-conflict, Trauma, Spirituality, Reconciliation

INTRODUCTION

The Poso Communal Conflict, which took place in the district of Poso, Central Sulawesi, Indonesia, from December 25, 1998 to December 20, 2001, resulted in significant material losses and casualties (Wijaya, 2020, pp. 58-63). Triggered by economic rivalry between the predominantly Christian indigenous population and the predominantly Muslim migrant population, the conflict led to mass rioting. The aftermath included 557 deaths, 384 injured, some 7,932 houses destroyed, and some 510 public places and facilities burned. The conflict was further fueled by demographic changes resulting from the transmigration program (NaskahHistoria, 2023).

The Poso conflict, one of Indonesia's longest (Wijaya, 2020, pp. 58-63), involved multiple parties (Ernita Krisandi, 2013, pp. 1-11) and resulted in changes in local governance and socioeconomic disparities (Bustan, 2016).. Post-conflict recovery in Poso is a long-term process requiring comprehensive efforts to restore security, law enforcement, and inter-ethnic and inter-religious reconciliation (Pemerintah Lakukan Langkah Terpadu untuk Selesaikan Konflik Poso, 2023). The recovery process involves rebuilding the social and religious identities of affected communities, which requires cooperation between the government, community institutions such as churches, and other stakeholders. Churches play a vital role in communities, providing places of worship and social services, addressing issues of education, health care, social

¹ The area called "Poso Kota Bersaudara" consists of three sub-districts, namely, Poso Kota, Poso Kota Utara, and Poso Kota Selatan. BPS Poso District, Regional Statistics of Poso District 2021 (December 2021), 1.

injustice, and immigration. Their undeniable positive impact on society is evident through their involvement in various charitable organizations and public service initiatives (Essays, 2023).

Christian communities play a crucial role in Poso's social development, including post-conflict reconstruction, humanitarian aid, peace-building and community restoration (Kristen, 2021). The church also promotes regional prosperity and peace through education, health, and community development ministries. Despite its significant role, the church faces challenges such as resource scarcity, social and political pressures, and the complexity of facilitating reconciliation (Laukapitang, 2016). The belief that the church should focus solely on spiritual matters is also a challenge in promoting social development.

METHODS

Twenty-five years after the end of the conflict, this study aims to assess the successes and challenges of the Christian Church in its social development mission in Poso. It seeks to understand the role of the church in post-conflict social development and measure its achievements in Poso Kota Bersaudara. The research provides insights into the church's role in holistic reconciliation, spiritual and psychological recovery, and community development.

This research uses qualitative methods (Matthew B. Miles, 2009) to understand the evaluation of success or challenges faced by the Christian Church in achieving the mission of social development in Poso Kota Bersaudara after 25 years of post-conflict (Moleong, 2010). These methods include literature review, field observations, in-depth interviews, and key informant selection. Through this combination of methods, the research aims to provide an in-depth understanding of the role of the Christian Church in post-conflict social development in Poso, while providing a detailed assessment of the successes or challenges it has faced. Data will be analyzed using qualitative techniques such as content analysis and constant comparison (Moleong, 2010).

THEORETICAL CONSTRUCTIONS

Post-conflict Social Development

Post-conflict social development, as defined by Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 7 of 2012 (Undang-undang RI, 2012) involves the restoration of communities and the reconstruction of infrastructure. Community development, as defined by Ulum (2013), aims to improve socio-economic-cultural conditions (Ulum, 2013). Tzifakis (2024) describes post-conflict reconstruction as a multifaceted task involving military, political, economic, and social improvements (Tzifakis, 2024). Lederach's (1997) framework for conflict resolution includes structure, process, reconciliation, resources, and coordination (Lederach, 1997). Conflict, as Tzifakis (2024) notes, has a devastating effect on human, social, and physical resources (Tzifakis, 2024).

Conflict affects spirituality (Williams, 2017) and psychology, as seen in Poso (cf. Day 2023, 75-104). The Poso conflict resulted in psychological effects (Wietse A. Tol, 2010) and social segregation (SNPK-THC, 2014, p. 32), which affected residential areas, daily interactions, community peace, and social cooperation (Panggabean, 2020). It has also had a devastating impact on the economy (Thai-Ha Le, 2022). Despite the government's efforts, the church plays a crucial role in Poso's post-conflict social development.

The Church in Social Development Mission

The church, as defined by Chia (Chia, 2021), both as an organism and an organization, plays a crucial role in social development and post-conflict reconstruction (Laukapitang, 2016). It promotes tolerance, mutual respect, and cooperation among religions (Lukito, 1991) and

contributes to social development through interfaith harmony, social assistance, and development activities (Kabupaten Poso, 2024). However, it often neglects its active social role (Laukapitang, 2016).

Through the promotion of moral behavior, the church has made a significant contribution to social development and to the reconstruction of post-conflict societies (Wahana Visi Indonesia, 2022), character building (S. Henderina A. Pello, 2021), community development, societal efficiency, resource development, and conflict reconciliation. It also critiques the prevailing social system and advocates for the oppressed (<https://repository.uksw.edu>, t.t.).

Christian education is key to post-conflict social development, building peace and character in the younger generation (Imelda Butarbutar, 2022). Civic education trains students to solve social problems, including conflict, by developing analytical skills and an understanding of social dynamics (Tuhuteru, 2021). Both Islam and Christianity contribute to post-conflict social integration (Retnowati, 2014). The Church's contribution is not only spiritual, but also provides practical guidance based on biblical principles, which has a significant impact on the post-conflict social context (Imelda Butarbutar, 2022).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The role of the Christian Church in post-conflict social development in Poso District and Poso Kota Bersaudara is significant, addressing the needs of the community since the reconciliation process. However, improvements are needed 25 years after the conflict. The Governor of Central Sulawesi recognizes the Christian Church of Central Sulawesi (GKST) for its role in various social development programs. Although not widely documented, some articles outline GKST's role in regional development (Redaksi Harian Mercusuar, 2023). The implementation of conflict management strategies is also part of these social development efforts (Kalembiro, 2018).

The Context of "Church" in the Poso of Kota Bersaudara Region

Based on data from the Ministry of Religious Affairs in 2020, around 60.80% (151,261 people) of the population of Poso regency embraced Christianity, with 59.45% (147,899 people) practicing Protestantism and 1.35% (3,362 people) practicing Catholicism. Meanwhile, Islam accounts for 33.60% (83,597 people), Hinduism 5.60% (13,937 people), and a small proportion of Buddhism, less than 0.01% (4 people) (Kabupaten Poso, 2024).

Data from Poso District Statistics Center, 2014 shows a comparison of the percentage of Muslims and Christians in a number of areas in Poso District. That the majority of the population in the Poso Kota Bersaudara area embraces Islam (Poso Kota, Islam: 98.53%, Christian: 1,16%. Poso Kota Utara, Islam: 87.73%, Christianity: 11,49%. South Poso Kota, Islam: 26.33%, Christianity: 73.28%), while the majority in other areas are Christian (Pemeluk Agama Menurut Kecamatan (persen), 2012-2014).

In the Poso Kota Bersaudara area there are Forty Two (42) Local Churches, as well as Thirteen (13) denominations spread across three sub-districts. In Poso Kota: Two (2) churches, North Poso Kota: Nine (9), and South Poso Kota: Thirty-one (31) churches (Poso, 2023). The data highlights the unique religious dynamics of Poso Kota Bersaudara, where the majority practice Islam, but there is also significant Christian diversity, as evidenced by the number of churches and denominations.

This data is crucial for assessing the successes and challenges of churches in their social development mission in Poso, 25 years after the conflict. It helps to understand the religious

diversity of the region, the distribution of churches, and the social and religious dynamics that influence the social development mission of the church in Poso Kota Bersaudara.

Reconciliation

Peace efforts in Poso involved the government, churches, customary institutions and Islamic organizations. Key steps included the formation by Sulawesi governors of "Rujuk Sintuwu Maroso" (Building Strong Unity), a group of 13 customary council leaders. On August 22, 2000, President Wahid visited Poso, and the Rujuk Sintuwu Maroso agreement was publicly read in the Pamona language. Early in the conflict, Regent Arif Patanga convened a regional leadership meeting with various parties to strategize solutions to the violence (Lembaga Ilmu Pengetahuan Indonesia, Current Asia and the Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue, 2011, pp. 57-58).

In November 2001, Arnold R. Tobondo took the important step of traveling to Jakarta to meet with the Coordinating Minister for Politics, Law and Security (Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono), the Coordinating Minister for Social Welfare (Jusuf Kalla) and the Minister of Defense (Abdul Jalil). Tobondo urged the government to actively address the conflict in Poso. This action showed the willingness of the Christian community in general to achieve peace (Lembaga Ilmu Pengetahuan Indonesia, Current Asia and the Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue, 2011, p. 60).

Although Tobondo told *Tribun Timur.com* that "Puang Jusuf Kalla was the first person to initiate peace in Central Sulawesi (Imtiyaaz, 2023)," in fact this peace effort was the initiative of Arnold Tobondo, under the auspices of the GKST Church Synod, who contacted the Coordinating Minister for Political and Security Affairs, Susilo Bambang Yudhoyono, the Coordinating Minister for People's Welfare and Poverty Alleviation, A, Jusuf Kalla, and the Minister of Defense, Abdul Jalil. At that time, Tobondo received a positive response from the government through the Menkokesra, Jusuf Kalla, who was then appointed to lead the mediation in the peace efforts in Poso. He was from Sulawesi and had a wide and strong network in Sulawesi (<https://repository.uksw.edu, t.t.>).

Within the Christian community, a meeting of community leaders was held in Tentena to determine which representatives to send to the peace talks in Malino. Twenty-three delegates were selected from throughout the conflict area, including representatives from academia, youth, and religious leaders. Two women from the Christian community of Tentena participated in the peace talks in Poso, demonstrating the equal participation of different levels of the Christian community in peace efforts (Lembaga Ilmu Pengetahuan Indonesia, Current Asia and the Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue, 2011, p. 60).

Since the beginning of the reconciliation process, the Church's service to the people has shown significant results. Aditjondro, revealed that while the ten-point agreement of the Malino Declaration (December 19-20, 2001, auth.) began to be socialized, the security disturbances in Poso and Morowali districts, which had been separated from their parent districts, began to change shape. Fighting between the two communities has practically ceased and the security disturbances have turned into terror by "unidentified groups" against the people of the two districts (Aditjondro, 2004). This means that the Christian community in the Poso region has consistently upheld the common commitment contained in the Malino Declaration. This is an indicator of the success of the church in promoting the community in the context of reconciliation.

Challenges such as post-conflict insecurity and maintaining reconciliation commitments are faced by the Christian Church in Poso. Nevertheless, it has made significant contributions to community development and reconciliation as reflected in the Malino Declaration commitments.

Multidimensional Service

In their efforts to maintain peace, promote harmony and contribute to the process of community recovery and development, the churches in the Poso Kota Bersaudara area continue to fulfill their roles. Despite various obstacles, the multidimensional ministry efforts continue.

Education

Over time, 25 years after the Poso conflict, the church continues to play a central role in social development efforts, as evidenced by its support for innovative programs. For example, the Coordinating Minister for People's Welfare (Menko Kesra) initiated the construction of the Tentena Christian University in 2007, and the church responded positively (Lembaga Ilmu Pengetahuan Indonesia, Current Asia and the Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue, 2011, p. 62).

The church's proactive role in Tentena is highlighted by the establishment of a university that promotes higher education and intellectual growth. Its commitment to education is evident in the sustained growth of Christian schools, which foster a faith-based learning environment that embraces diversity. Despite religious segregation, the development of these schools underscores the church's commitment to education as part of its social development mission. The message of a culture of peace through education is also being carried out in other conflict areas, such as West Kalimantan (2017). In his study entitled "Peace Education Through Religious Education at High Schools in Post-Conflict Areas," Atmanto found that "religious education plays an important role in conveying the message of a culture of peace education (Atmanto, 2017, p. 165)."

The church in Poso has a significant role in education, not only through the provision of Christian schools from early childhood through high school, but also through the inculcation of moral and spiritual values. Despite enrollment restrictions based on religion, the church's consistent maintenance and development of these institutions underscores its commitment to holistic education and community development.

Ecumenical

In Poso Kota Bersaudara, churches are implementing effective social development programs. In 2019, the Oikoumene Fellowship of Churches in Ranononcu was established to strengthen interchurch cooperation. This initiative supports the social development vision of the region. In the initial stages of this research, the author interviewed Atriadi Usman, pastor of Ranononcu Bethany Church since 2008, and Martinus Elvis Bonggili of the Poso Christian Religious Board. The Oikoumene Fellowship's programs include monthly worship services, joint Christmas and Easter celebrations, diaconal services, creative business training, relationship covenants, and community development.

In the interview, Usman explained that "the monthly worship service is the main foundation for inter-church cooperation, while the joint Christmas and Easter activities aim to strengthen the spirit of togetherness among all church members (Usman, 2023)." The Fellowship also faced several obstacles in implementing the program. In response to the question, "What are the obstacles in the implementation of this program?" he said, "The rotation of pastors is done periodically in several denominations. As a result of this change, fellow servants of God have to adapt to the new environment (Usman, 2023)."

There are other obstacles that Usman observes: "There is also exclusivism and antipathy among the lay congregation, as well as problems with family relationships that often spill over into shared ministry. These things often make it difficult (Usman, 2023)." However, the positive impact of the Oikoumene Fellowship is very visible. In this regard, Usman explains, that the partnership has increased the closeness and solidarity among the churches in Ranononcu. The sense of brotherhood among the congregations is stronger, creating a harmonious atmosphere. Open

communication between church leaders also speeds up the resolution of problems that arise, creating close relationships among the servants of God and better cooperation (Usman, 2023).

The Oikoumene fellowship of churches in the village of Ranononcu has significantly strengthened interchurch relations and improved community services. Despite challenges, this spirit of cooperation is expected to inspire other churches in their social development efforts and positively impact their regions. This spirit is also crucial in non-conflict areas such as the Toraja region. As Sapan's research highlights, mutual respect between denominations is essential to building an ecumenical spirit and fostering good relationships to work together in serving God and the community (Sapan, 2021, pp. 59-75)."

The inaugural fellowship in Poso Kota Bersaudara addresses the long-standing problem of a declining ecumenical spirit among churches. Recognizing this persistent challenge is crucial to ensuring the growth of the ecumenical spirit, which is essential for fostering brotherhood and religious harmony. Continued attention is needed to ensure that this spirit becomes a fundamental part of church efforts in the region.

Interfaith Relationships

The launch of "Religious Moderation in Indonesia," a program that aims to build a moderate religious life and strengthen religious harmony in Indonesia (Humas, 2022). The program was initiated by the Ministry of Religious Affairs and involved various stakeholders, including the Buddhist Religious Council, the Religious Harmony Forum, and religious and community leaders (Redaksi, 2019). The program includes various activities such as the declaration of the Year of Tolerance, the establishment of moderation villages, and the formation of religious moderation villages. The program also includes efforts to combat misinformation and promote mainstream religious moderation (Tala, 2023).

On December 6, 2023, the authors conducted an interesting interview with Ratna Lagonda, the Chairperson of the GKST Klasis Poso Kota Church Council. On this occasion, she enthusiastically described the concrete programs carried out by the Church in supporting interfaith cooperation, especially in the Religious Moderation program. Lagonda said, "the theme of our activities is 'Caring for Harmony & Knitting Togetherness' (Lagonda, 2023)." The GKST Klasis Poso Kota Church initiated this program with the aim of strengthening interfaith relations in the region. Lagonda, also shared the challenges and obstacles faced during the implementation of this program. He said that, "during the implementation of this program, we used our own funds, there was no support from other parties, especially the local government (Lagonda, 2023)." Here, the lack of support from the Poso Regional Government is the main obstacle highlighted.

Meanwhile, she says, "there is pessimism and antipathy from some church leaders. This creates internal challenges that need to be overcome (Lagonda, 2023)." According to her testimony, there are also psychological challenges. She says "there is a sense of suspicion and anxiety from the general public, as well as the church congregation towards different groups (Lagonda, 2023)." Also "due to a lack of support (Lagonda, 2023)," she continued, "Funding constraints are a significant factor affecting the smooth running of the program (Lagonda, 2023)."

On the other hand, despite facing significant challenges, Ratna Lagonda expressed her hopes regarding the Religious Moderation program. First, she hopes that the Poso Regional Government will provide greater support to their community in running the program, to strengthen interfaith harmony in the Poso Kota Bersaudara region. "I hope the local government can support us more in executing these religious moderation programs (Lagonda, 2023)." At the end of this interview Lagonda expressed some hopes

I hope that there will be a change in the attitude of church leaders who are still pessimistic, creating an environment that supports interfaith cooperation. In addition, I also hope for an educative approach that can open up the understanding and openness of the community and church congregations towards different groups, especially Muslims. Finally, there is greater financial support, both from within the church and externally, to ensure the smooth implementation of the program and achieve the desired goals (Lagonda, 2023).

GKST Church of Poso Kota Klasis has a strong commitment to promoting interfaith harmony and creating a harmonious environment. Through the Religious Moderation Program, it proactively contributes to social development and harmony despite facing complex challenges.

Rehabilitation (Psychology & Spirituality)

The psychological trauma that remains after conflict is inevitable, but it is often ignored (Natar, 2019, pp. 1-21), especially against civilians. In the *Journal of Social Science & Medicine* (2013), The researchers point out that the number of armed conflicts involving civilians has increased over the past three decades, resulting in more physical and psychological harm. While soldiers receive medical care and reintegration support after combat, similar support is lacking for civilians. The impact of war-related trauma on civilians and their challenges in achieving employment success after trauma are areas that need more attention (Elizabeth A.M. Searing, 2013).

Related to the necessities above, through observation, it was found that in 2018, the GKI Sul-Sel Jemaat Poso church launched the Inner Wounds Recovery Service Program as an initiative to provide spiritual support to youth and adolescents who experienced trauma in the past.

The Inner Wounds Recovery Service Program of GKI Sul-Sel Jemaat Poso aims to provide spiritual guidance to participants in need of inner healing. Despite high enthusiasm with about twenty active participants, the program, originally planned to be periodic, was disrupted by the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020 and has since been conducted on an occasional and personal basis. The church hopes to resume the program. Focused on spiritual recovery and biblical values, the program demonstrates the Church's commitment to the psychological well-being of its members and its role in social development by providing support and guidance. (Gereja GKI Poso, 2018).

GKI Sul-Sel Jemaat Poso's Inner Wounds Recovery Service Program supports the psychological well-being of its members and demonstrates the church's role in social development. It aids recovery from conflict trauma and is key to the church's post-conflict mission in Poso Kota Bersaudara. Despite challenges, the positive impact of the program is evident, highlighting the need for continued support to sustain and grow this initiative.

Reconstruction

In addition to the casualties & injuries, on December 5, 2001, the Government also published data that there were "7,932 houses destroyed, and 510 public facilities burned or damaged (Kerusuhan Poso, 2023)." In this context, the Church has also played a role, being involved in the physical recovery and reconstruction efforts needed to restore life to the postconflict Poso Kota Bersaudara community. Ande Walkamdi, an assembly member at GKST Baithel Sayo Church, Poso, recounted his experience in 2001, saying that:

after the riots many people, especially Christians, including my family, lost their homes due to arson by the other side. Well, at that time there was information that there was housing assistance from the GPdI Church Synod. After I searched for information, it turned out to be true, and long story short our family and several families in this complex received this assistance, even the body of this house, most of it is still that assistance. (Walkamdi, 2023).

Walkamdi also asserted that “no other church is implementing such a program here (Walkamdi, 2023).” This information underscores the special role of the GPdI Church Synod in providing tangible assistance to communities affected by the unrest.

The GPdI Synod's housing program for Christians displaced by the 2001 conflict demonstrates the church's commitment to its community and its role in social development. The program, which is unique and sustainable compared to other regional initiatives, provides housing as a form of long-term recovery assistance to conflict-affected communities in Poso Kota Bersaudara. This analysis shows that the role of the church in post-conflict physical recovery in Poso Kota Bersaudara has a positive impact. This is unique, given that elsewhere this role has been taken on by the government, for example in Maluku Province in 2021 (Adjis, 2022).

The importance of inter-church coordination in social development, especially in post-conflict scenarios, is emphasized by the GPdI Church Synod. Such coordination enables churches to work together for sustainable social impact. The focus is on the longevity of physical reconstruction programs and the promotion of synergy between churches and communities for holistic social development. This collaborative approach integrates immediate action into a broader framework, aligning resources and knowledge for a comprehensive approach to social development that leads to long-term positive change.

The Economy

In addition to the work done by the Oikoumene Fellowship as expressed by Usman before (Usman, 2023), Church encouragement in Economic growth is also found in Rehobot Poso Toraja Church. This was reported in Mosintuwu Journal: Journal of Community Service, April 2022 edition, entitled “Entrepreneurship Training for Young People of the Youth Fellowship of the Toraja Church Rehobot Poso Congregation.”

In the article Tabita R. Matana and Ita Mowidu, reported that the youth members of the Toraja church in Rehobot Poso congregation who participated in this activity amounted to Thirty Eight (38) people, consisting of high school students and university students (Tabita R. Matana, 2022, pp. 21-23). This activity showed positive results and impacts. 90% of participants acknowledged their lack of understanding of self-employment prior to the training. Outcomes of the training included a better understanding of the concept of self-employment, motivation for participants to engage in self-employment despite the risks and large capital requirements, and reinforcement for youth members who have started their own businesses, particularly in the barbershop sector (Tabita R. Matana, 2022).

Church cooperation and entrepreneurship training activities have had a positive impact on socio-economic development. These initiatives educate young people about self-employment and encourage them to start businesses. The Rehobot Poso Toraja Church's support for entrepreneurial youth has contributed significantly to community development. The analysis underscores the role of the church in post-conflict economic recovery and the importance of sustaining such programs and coordinating with the government for broader, sustainable results..

CONCLUSION

This research examines the role of the church in social development in Poso, a region that has experienced communal conflict for 25 years. The church has been active in improving inter-church and inter-religious relations, the quality of community life, and providing spiritual support. However, these efforts have been local and confessional, limiting their impact. The research suggests that interchurch cooperation needs to be improved and inclusive strategies developed for broader impact. A key challenge is to promote a common understanding of "religious moderation" among believers for holistic social development. Ongoing dialogue among church members and stakeholders is emphasized to align on the values of religious moderation. The

research aims to guide the church and related parties in formulating effective strategies for social development in post-conflict environments such as Poso.

References

- Aditjondro, G. J. (2004). Kerusuhan Poso dan Morowali, Akar Permasalahan dan Jalan Keluarnya. *Penerapan Keadaan Darurat di Aceh, Papua dan Poso Dalam Pemilu 2004?* (p. 4). Jakarta: https://www.academia.edu/29706102/KERUSUHAN_POSO_DAN_MOROWALI_AKAR_PERMASALAHAN_DAN_JALAN_KELUARNYA.
- Adjis, R. (2022, Januari 27). *Terasmaluku.com*. Retrieved Januari 17, 2024, from <https://terasmaluku.com/headline/2022/01/27/distribusi-bantuan-pos-keamanan-dan-identifikasi-rumah-terbakar-jadi-fokus-penanganan-pasca-konflik-ori-kariuw/>
- Afrizal Tjoetra, S. (2016). *PPID-Aceh*. Retrieved Januari 15, 2024, from ppid2.acehprov.go.id: https://ppid2.acehprov.go.id/v2/articles/read/60
- Atmanto, N. E. (2017). Pendidikan Damai Melalui Pendidikan Agama Pada Sekolah Menengah Atas di Daerah Pasca Konflik (Studi di SMA St. Fransiskus Asisi Bengkayang & SMA Shalom Bengkayang). *Jurnal SMART (Studi Masyarakat Religi dan Tradisi)*, 155-168.
- Badan Pusat Statistik Kab. Poso, , diakses pada 16 Januari 2024. . (2014). Retrieved Januari 16, 2024, from www.posokab.bps.go.id: www.posokab.bps.go.id
- Bustan, T. S. (2016). *Media Indonesia*. Retrieved November 28, 2023, from mediaindonesia.com: https://mediaindonesia.com/nusantara/69088/pemulihan-poso-butuh-waktu-lama
- Chia, P. S. (2021). The Word Ekklēsia in Matthew and Its Implication for Social Justice. *Biblical Theology Bulletin* 51 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146107920980932>, 51, 24-32. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1177/0146107920980932>.
- Elizabeth A.M. Searing, F. R.-A. (2013). The impact of psychological trauma on wages in post-conflict Bosnia and Herzegovina. *Social Science & Medicine*, 165-173.
- Ernita Krisandi, B. S. (2013). Resolusi Konflik Komunal di Maluku Pasca Reformasi. *Jurnal Ilmu Pemerintahan*, 1-11.
- Essays, F. (2023, Maret). *Freshessays*. Retrieved Januari 15, 2024, from <https://samples.freshessays.com/the-roles-churches-play-in-social-welfare-and-society.html>
- Ezra Tari, J. I. (2020, Agustus). Gereja dalam Realitas Sosial Indonesia Masa Kini. *Jurnal Teruna Bhakti*, Vol. 3, 25-35.
- Gereja GKI Poso. (2018). *Laporan Pelayanan Gereja GKI Poso*. Poso: GKI Poso.
- Humas, T. (2022, Oktober 17). *Ditjen Bimas Budha Kementerian Agama RI*. Retrieved Januari 9, 2024, from <https://bimasbuddha.kemenag.go.id/supriyadi-pencanangan-tahun-toleransi-mewujudkan-kehidupan-beragama-yang-moderat-berita-901.html>
- Imelda Butarbutar, D. R. (2022). Pendidikan Perdamaian dalam Perspektif Pendidikan Agama Kristen Sebagai Upaya Meminimalisasi Konflik dan Kekerasan Antar Mahasiswa di Universitas HKBP Nommensen Medan. *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Konseling*, 4, 6962-6972. Retrieved Januari 17, 2024, from <file:///C:/Users/ACER/Downloads/9416-Article%20Text-28750-2-10-20221128.pdf>
- Imtiyaz, F. (2023, Mei 15). *Tribun Timur.Com*. Retrieved Desember 5, 2023, from <https://makassar.tribunnews.com/2023/05/15/pdt-arnold-tobondo-kenang-perjuangan-jk-damaikan-poso-2001-dia-ditakdirkan-tuhan-selamatkan-bangsa>
- Kalembiro, R. (2018). *Implementasi Kebijakan Penanggulangan Konflik (Studi Pada Implementasi Peraturan Daerah No 2 Tahun 2013 Tentang Penanggulangan Bencana Di Kabupaten Poso Provinsi Sulawesi Tengah)*. Malang: Universitas Brawijaya.
- Kristen, T. M. (2021, Oktober 31). *Kementerian Agama Republik Indonesia*. Retrieved Januari 15, 2024, from <https://kemenag.go.id/kristen/peranan-gereja-dalam-mewujudkan-keadilan-sosial-3f37jd>

- Lagonda, R. (2023, Desember 6). Merawat Kerukunan & Merajut Kebersamaan. (P. G. Sunkudon, Interviewer) Kasintuwu, Poso.
- Larat, I. (2023). Peran Gereja Katolik Dalam Memperjuangkan Kemanusiaan Atas Konflik di Maluku. *Jurnal Fides Et Ratio*, 48-62.
- Laukapitang, Y. D. (2016). Teologi Pembangunan Berbasis Pengembangan Masyarakat Shalom Pada Gereja Kemah Injil Indonesia Daerah Kupang Nusa Tenggara Timur. *Jurnal Jaffray*, vol. 14. Retrieved Januari 15, 2024, from <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/104009-teologi-pembangunan-berbasis-pengembanga-b91ad8ec.pdf>
- Lederach, J. P. (1997). *Building Peace: Sustainable Reconciliation in Divided Societies*. Washington, DC: United States Institute of Peace Press.
- Lembaga Ilmu Pengetahuan Indonesia, Current Asia and the Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue. (2011). *Pengelolaan Konflik di Indonesia – Sebuah Analisis Konflik di Maluku, Papua dan Poso*. Lausanne: Centre for Humanitarian Dialogue.
- Lukito, D. L. (1991). *repository.seabs.ac.id*. Retrieved Januari 17, 2024, from [seabs.ac.id](https://repository.seabs.ac.id/bitstream/handle/123456789/676/Kecenderungan%20gerakan%20Oikumene%20dewasa%20ini.pdf), : <https://repository.seabs.ac.id/bitstream/handle/123456789/676/Kecenderungan%20gerakan%20Oikumene%20dewasa%20ini.pdf>
- Matthew B. Miles, A. M. (2009). *Analisis Data Kualitatif*. (M. Tjetjep Rohendi Rohidi, Trans.) Jakarta: Penerbit Universitas Indonesia.
- Moleong, L. J. (2010). *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.
- NaskahHistoria. (2023, Februari 20). *Museum Perumusan Naskah Proklamasi*. Retrieved Januari 15, 2024, from <https://munasprok.or.id/ketahui-bagaimana-sejarah-terjadinya-perang-poso-1998-2001/>
- Natar, A. N. (2019). Trauma Healing bagi Perempuan Korban Konflik: Belajar dari Konflik Maluku dan Poso. *Dunamis: Jurnal Teologi dan Pendidikan Kristiani*, 1-21. Retrieved from <http://www.sttintheos.ac.id/e-journal/index.php/dunamis>
- Panggabean, R. (2020). *PUSAD Yayasan Wakaf Paramadina*. Retrieved Januari 15, 2024, from www.paramadina-pusad.or.id: <https://www.paramadina-pusad.or.id/penghindaran-positif-segregasi-dan-kerjasama-komunal-di-maluku/>
- Poso, A. K. (2023). Data Gereja Kab. Poso. .
- Redaksi Harian Mercusuar. (2023, September 13). *Mercusuar: Korannya Rakyat Sul-Teng*. Retrieved Desember 11, 2023, from <https://mercusuar.web.id/sulteng-membangun/gkst-berperan-penting-dalam-pembangunan-daerah/>
- Redaksi, T. (2019, April 16). *Kementerian Komunikasi & Informatika RI*. Retrieved Januari 9, 2024, from https://www.kominfo.go.id/content/detail/18041/kemenag-terus-prioritaskan-program-pengarusutamaan-moderasi-beragama/0/artikel_gpr
- repository.uksw.edu*. (n.d.). Retrieved Januari 15, 2024, from [uksw.edu](https://repository.uksw.edu/bitstream/123456789/734/3/D_902008102_BAB%20II.pdf): https://repository.uksw.edu/bitstream/123456789/734/3/D_902008102_BAB%20II.pdf
- Retnowati. (2014). Agama, Konflik, Dan Integrasi Sosial. *Jurnal Analisa*, 21, 189-200. Retrieved Januari 17, 2024, from <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/41938-ID-agama-konflik-dan-integrasi-sosial-integrasi-sosial-pasca-konflik-situbondo.pdf>
- S. Henderina A. Pello, P. S. (2021). Peran Gereja dalam Pembangunan Karakter sebagai Bentuk Tanggung Jawab Membangun Bangsa. *Prosiding Pelita Bangsa*, 156-160.
- Sapan, E. B. (2021). Oikumene: Kehidupan Oikumene Gereja Toraja Dengan Gereja Pentakosta di Indonesia Bagi Kehidupan Bermasyarakat di Kecamatan Bittuang Kabupaten Tana Toraja. *Kamasean: Jurnal Teologi Kristen*, 59-75.
- SNPK-THC, T. (2014). *Segregasi, Kekerasan dan Kebijakan Rekonstruksi Pascakonflik di Ambon (Program Sistem Nasional Pemantauan Kekerasan)*. Depok : SNPK-THC. Retrieved Januari 15, 2024, from <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/45146-ID-segregasi-ke>
- (t.t., t.b.). Retrieved Desember 12, 2023, from https://repository.uksw.edu:https://repository.uksw.edu/bitstream/123456789/10517/2/T1_752013032_BAB%20II.pdf
- Tabita R. Matana, I. M. (2022). Pelatihan Kewirausahaan Kaum Muda Persekutuan Pemuda Gereja Toraja Jemaat Rehobot Poso. *Mosintuwu : Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 21-23.

- Tala, H. K. (2023, Juli 4). *Kantor Kementerian Agama Kab. Tanah Laut*. Retrieved Januari 9 Januari 2024, 2024, from <https://tanahlaut.kemenag.go.id/read/850/ketua-fkub-moderasi-beragama-perkuat-kerukunan-umat-beragama>
- Tempo.co.* (2023). Retrieved November 28, 2023, from <https://nasional.tempo.co/read/20316/pemerintah-lakukan-langkah-terpadu-untuk-selesaikan-konflik-poso>
- Thai-Ha Le, M.-T. B. (2022). Economic and social impacts of conflict: A cross-country analysis. *Economic Modelling*, 1-13. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econmod.2022.105980>
- Trijono, L. (2009). Pembangunan Perdamaian Pasca-Konflik di Indonesia: Kaitan perdamaian, pembangunan dan demokrasi dalam pengembangan kelembagaan pasca-konflik. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial dan Ilmu Politik*, 13, 48-70. Retrieved Januari 15, 2024
- Tuhuteru, L. (2021). Pengaruh Situasi Pasca Konflik Sosial Terhadap Pembelajaran Pkn Di Sekolah. *Jurnal PEKAN*, 6, 50-65. Retrieved Januari 17, 2024, from file:///C:/Users/ACER/Downloads/1167-3733-1-SM.pdf
- Tzifakis, N. (2024). "Postconflict Economic Reconstruction," dalam *Encyclopedia Princetoniensis*. Retrieved Januari 11, 2024, from <https://pesd.princeton.edu/node/586>
- Ulum, R. (2013, Juni). Prospek Pembangunan Masyarakat Pasca Konflik Sambas. *Jurnal Analisa*, 20, 25-35. doi:10.18784/analisa.v20i1.3
- Undang-undang RI. (2012). *Kemenkeu*. Retrieved Januari 10, 2024, from [Kemenkeu.go.id: https://jdih.kemenkeu.go.id/fullText/2012/7TAHUN2012UU.PDF](https://jdih.kemenkeu.go.id/fullText/2012/7TAHUN2012UU.PDF)
- Usman, A. (2023, Desember 9). Persekutuan Oikoumene Gereja-gereja se-Kelurahan Ranononcu. (P. G. Sunkudon, Interviewer) Ranononcu, Poso.
- Wahana Visi Indonesia. (2022, November 25). <https://wahanavisi.org/id>. Retrieved Desember 20, 2023, from <https://wahanavisi.org/id/media-materi/cerita/detail/gereja-kristen-dan-kontribusinya-dalam-mewujudkan-kesejahteraan>
- Walkamdi, A. (2023, Desember 5). Bantuan Perumahan Sinode GPdI. (P. G. Sunkudon, Interviewer) Poso, Sulawesi tengah.
- Wietse A. Tol, R. R. (2010). Communal violence and child psychosocial well-being: qualitative findings from Poso, Indonesia. *Transcultural Psychiatry* 47, no. 1, 112-135. Retrieved Desember 12, 2023, from <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1363461510364573>
- Wijaya, N. (2020). Resolusi Konflik Berbasis Budaya Oleh Masyarakat Kabupaten Poso. *Jurnal Kolaborasi Resolusi Konflik*, 58-63.
- Wikipedia.* (2023, Juni 4). Retrieved Januari 10, 2024, from https://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kerusuhan_Poso
- Wikipedia.* (2024). Retrieved Januari 16, 2024, from https://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kabupaten_Poso#Kecamatan.
- Williams, W. (2017, July 18). *Biola University Center for Marriage and Relationships*. Retrieved Desember 12, 2023, from <https://cmr.biola.edu>: <https://cmr.biola.edu/blog/2017/jul/18/5-reasons-to-communicate-and-resolve-conflict-from-a-spiritual-perspective/>